

Supplementary Information

S1: SQL Query for filtering pre-training dataset from the Imaging Data Commons	2
S2: Flowchart for filtering pre-training dataset from the Imaging Data Commons	3
S3: Extended Comparison of CT-FM against other approaches on MSD dataset	4
S4: Extended Comparison of CT-FM against other approaches on the TotalSegmentatorV2 dataset	12
S5: IDC collections used with the number of scans sourced from them and a short description of the collection.	22

```

WITH
  idc_instances_per_series AS (
    SELECT
      SeriesInstanceUID,
      COUNT(DISTINCT(SOPInstanceUID)) AS num_instances,
      COUNT(DISTINCT(ARRAY_TO_STRING(ImagePositionPatient, "/"))) AS position_count,
      MAX(SAFE_CAST(SliceThickness AS float64)) AS max_SliceThickness,
      MIN(SAFE_CAST(SliceThickness AS float64)) AS min_SliceThickness,
      STRING_AGG(DISTINCT(SAFE_CAST("LOCALIZER" IN UNNEST(ImageType) AS string)), "") AS
has_localizer
    FROM
      `bigquery-public-data.idc_v14.dicom_all`
    WHERE
      Modality = "CT" and
      access = "Public"
    GROUP BY
      SeriesInstanceUID)
SELECT
  dicom_all.SeriesInstanceUID,
  ANY_VALUE(dicom_all.collection_id) as collection_id,
  ANY_VALUE(dicom_all.PatientID) AS PatientID,
  ANY_VALUE(idc_instances_per_series.num_instances) AS num_instances,
  ANY_VALUE(CONCAT("https://viewer.imaging.datacommons.cancer.gov/viewer/",
dicom_all.StudyInstanceUID, "?seriesInstanceUID=", dicom_all.SeriesInstanceUID)) AS
idc_url
FROM
  `bigquery-public-data.idc_v18.dicom_all` AS dicom_all
JOIN
  idc_instances_per_series
ON
  dicom_all.SeriesInstanceUID = idc_instances_per_series.SeriesInstanceUID
WHERE
  idc_instances_per_series.min_SliceThickness >= 1
  AND idc_instances_per_series.max_SliceThickness <= 5
  AND idc_instances_per_series.num_instances > 50
  AND idc_instances_per_series.num_instances/idc_instances_per_series.position_count = 1
  AND has_localizer = "false"
GROUP BY
  SeriesInstanceUID

```

S1: SQL Query for filtering pre-training dataset from the Imaging Data Commons

S2: Flowchart for filtering pre-training dataset from the Imaging Data Commons

Label	CT-FM + Auto3DSe g	Auto3DSe g (our impl.)	Auto3DSe g	nnUNet	VISTA3D-a uto
Hepatic Tumor	0.695	0.681	0.616	0.617	0.588
Lung Tumor	0.610	0.532	0.562	0.554	0.614
Pancreatic Tumor	0.475	0.481	0.485	0.488	0.324
Hepatic (Vessel) Tumor	0.710	0.698	0.683	0.659	0.682

S3: Extended Comparison of CT-FM against other approaches on MSD dataset

	Auto3d Seg	nnUNet	TotalSegmentator	VISTA3 D auto	VISTA3 D point	VISTA3 D auto+point	CT FM (Ours)
spleen	0.957	0.969	0.982	0.967	0.965	0.971	0.975
right kidney	0.949	0.94	0.962	0.934	0.93	0.948	0.943
left kidney	0.942	0.922	0.961	0.92	0.921	0.941	0.936
gallbladder	0.807	0.843	0.896	0.827	0.782	0.833	0.801
liver	0.964	0.965	0.982	0.968	0.944	0.974	0.971
stomach	0.929	0.935	0.96	0.931	0.917	0.939	0.941
aorta	0.954	0.961	0.961	0.959	0.949	0.965	0.968
inferior vena cava	0.892	0.902	0.896	0.883	0.695	0.896	0.919
portal and splenic vein	0.757	0.83	0.835	0.801	0.744	0.818	0.803
pancreas	0.845	0.856	0.917	0.86	0.833	0.877	0.865
right adrenal gland	0.805	0.877	0.909	0.863	0.834	0.869	0.846
left adrenal gland	0.808	0.866	0.914	0.873	0.851	0.881	0.853
left lung upper lobe	0.943	0.939	0.979	0.953	0.931	0.955	0.963
left lung lower lobe	0.928	0.953	0.964	0.938	0.899	0.944	0.946

right lung upper lobe	0.896	0.938	0.952	0.918	0.872	0.905	0.875
right lung middle lobe	0.905	0.939	0.952	0.916	0.909	0.93	0.929
right lung lower lobe	0.928	0.95	0.974	0.943	0.893	0.951	0.950
vertebrae L5	0.909	0.93	0.946	0.916	0.916	0.933	0.926
vertebrae L4	0.899	0.929	0.947	0.899	0.917	0.933	0.914
vertebrae L3	0.892	0.927	0.967	0.925	0.934	0.957	0.918
vertebrae L2	0.925	0.928	0.975	0.936	0.95	0.968	0.936
vertebrae L1	0.904	0.917	0.964	0.919	0.934	0.955	0.919
vertebrae T12	0.902	0.932	0.961	0.902	0.93	0.952	0.915
vertebrae T11	0.899	0.922	0.97	0.9	0.93	0.952	0.912
vertebrae T10	0.9	0.918	0.972	0.901	0.937	0.955	0.905
vertebrae T9	0.886	0.918	0.976	0.901	0.936	0.96	0.896
vertebrae T8	0.882	0.893	0.967	0.872	0.913	0.949	0.869
vertebrae T7	0.822	0.886	0.92	0.831	0.89	0.92	0.829
vertebrae T6	0.84	0.902	0.943	0.878	0.91	0.933	0.865
vertebrae T5	0.869	0.923	0.944	0.891	0.904	0.93	0.888

vertebr ae T4	0.876	0.91	0.948	0.887	0.91	0.935	0.898
vertebr ae T3	0.888	0.926	0.95	0.895	0.903	0.935	0.908
vertebr ae T2	0.909	0.918	0.967	0.92	0.922	0.949	0.925
vertebr ae T1	0.907	0.945	0.969	0.933	0.926	0.95	0.939
vertebr ae C7	0.894	0.943	0.964	0.923	0.901	0.937	0.920
vertebr ae C6	0.839	0.84	0.941	0.852	0.864	0.912	0.874
vertebr ae C5	0.797	0.832	0.915	0.825	0.822	0.862	0.845
vertebr ae C4	0.86	0.859	0.944	0.904	0.881	0.917	0.890
vertebr ae C3	0.857	0.936	0.956	0.905	0.905	0.926	0.904
vertebr ae C2	0.908	0.953	0.972	0.91	0.872	0.933	0.914
vertebr ae C1	0.884	0.862	0.935	0.894	0.848	0.896	0.868
esopha gus	0.874	0.913	0.952	0.907	0.886	0.916	0.910
trachea	0.926	0.945	0.974	0.941	0.91	0.946	0.949
brain	0.87	0.946	0.943	0.894	0.892	0.903	0.894
left iliac artery	0.822	0.896	0.916	0.895	0.872	0.906	0.882
right iliac artery	0.82	0.879	0.915	0.875	0.877	0.899	0.881
left iliac vena	0.841	0.898	0.941	0.917	0.899	0.925	0.910
right iliac vena	0.834	0.884	0.919	0.89	0.846	0.908	0.885

small bowel	0.854	0.868	0.948	0.821	0.846	0.869	0.862
duodenum	0.779	0.805	0.9	0.822	0.869	0.901	0.828
colon	0.882	0.882	0.948	0.898	0.819	0.906	0.908
left rib 1	0.914	0.938	0.948	0.909	0.875	0.918	0.911
right rib 1	0.934	0.927	0.966	0.932	0.909	0.943	0.914
left rib 2	0.906	0.929	0.95	0.91	0.885	0.907	0.936
right rib 2	0.908	0.936	0.947	0.903	0.887	0.927	0.931
left rib 3	0.878	0.895	0.933	0.889	0.889	0.928	0.919
right rib 3	0.865	0.912	0.925	0.866	0.884	0.916	0.906
left rib 6	0.885	0.907	0.942	0.877	0.901	0.934	0.879
right rib 6	0.902	0.888	0.955	0.89	0.91	0.941	0.894
left rib 9	0.91	0.901	0.953	0.897	0.916	0.937	0.900
right rib 9	0.911	0.883	0.949	0.893	0.906	0.938	0.886
left rib 10	0.891	0.904	0.949	0.903	0.911	0.938	0.891
right rib 10	0.885	0.873	0.912	0.883	0.871	0.909	0.907
left rib 11	0.905	0.938	0.945	0.907	0.875	0.912	0.901
right rib 11	0.933	0.946	0.959	0.924	0.888	0.929	0.891
left rib 12	0.906	0.938	0.931	0.891	0.854	0.9	0.883
right rib 12	0.928	0.942	0.949	0.906	0.882	0.926	0.894
right rib 4	0.905	0.893	0.916	0.876	0.877	0.914	0.911

right rib 5	0.9	0.929	0.951	0.886	0.907	0.932	0.874
right rib 7	0.903	0.914	0.96	0.884	0.915	0.942	0.899
right rib 8	0.888	0.928	0.959	0.887	0.913	0.941	0.886
left humerus	0.911	0.867	0.93	0.854	0.881	0.903	0.902
right humerus	0.916	0.794	0.94	0.873	0.884	0.913	0.917
left scapula	0.91	0.949	0.959	0.911	0.887	0.921	0.931
right scapula	0.916	0.923	0.959	0.922	0.887	0.92	0.937
left clavicle	0.955	0.917	0.975	0.952	0.931	0.956	0.953
right clavicle	0.937	0.94	0.973	0.945	0.933	0.952	0.953
left femur	0.944	0.882	0.97	0.94	0.944	0.954	0.960
right femur	0.944	0.911	0.98	0.945	0.957	0.959	0.971
left hip	0.944	0.937	0.975	0.947	0.938	0.955	0.975
right hip	0.939	0.932	0.986	0.95	0.961	0.959	0.970
sacrum	0.925	0.933	0.958	0.914	0.925	0.922	0.942
left gluteus maximus	0.923	0.927	0.972	0.94	0.938	0.949	0.961
right gluteus maximus	0.917	0.93	0.978	0.937	0.937	0.949	0.959

left gluteus medius	0.919	0.926	0.973	0.931	0.923	0.923	0.947
right gluteus medius	0.908	0.927	0.978	0.938	0.937	0.946	0.958
left gluteus minimus	0.875	0.917	0.965	0.914	0.903	0.919	0.933
right gluteus minimus	0.876	0.92	0.967	0.915	0.896	0.921	0.935
left autochthon	0.939	0.934	0.978	0.951	0.932	0.953	0.964
right autochthon	0.941	0.932	0.976	0.941	0.927	0.947	0.961
left iliopsoas	0.876	0.91	0.965	0.921	0.898	0.926	0.934
right iliopsoas	0.876	0.916	0.952	0.907	0.898	0.914	0.925
bladder	0.89	0.906	0.934	0.899	0.895	0.915	0.916
left atrial appendage	0.864	0.906	0.942	0.901	0.873	0.91	0.905
brachiocephalic trunk	0.872	0.899	0.936	0.892	0.858	0.915	0.911
left brachiocephalic vein	0.881	0.919	0.942	0.904	0.885	0.898	0.919
right brachiocephalic	0.862	0.909	0.922	0.884	0.869	0.901	0.890

c vein							
left common carotid artery	0.826	0.884	0.925	0.868	0.828	0.891	0.879
right common carotid artery	0.755	0.858	0.885	0.811	0.784	0.844	0.818
costal cartilages	0.844	0.868	0.888	0.856	0.833	0.864	0.862
heart	0.932	0.928	0.937	0.919	0.916	0.924	0.936
left kidney cyst	0.623	0.858	0.892	0.618	0.752	0.858	0.449
right kidney cyst	0.568	0.841	0.716	0.606	0.615	0.681	0.277
prostate	0.743	0.752	0.808	0.744	0.745	0.774	0.759
pulmonary vein	0.838	0.82	0.916	0.83	0.747	0.863	0.877
skull	0.909	0.849	0.893	0.827	0.769	0.857	0.871
spinal cord	0.911	0.95	0.959	0.934	0.905	0.911	0.936
sternum	0.896	0.906	0.897	0.899	0.884	0.911	0.920
left subclavian artery	0.833	0.901	0.929	0.877	0.857	0.892	0.891
right subclavian artery	0.818	0.87	0.916	0.861	0.85	0.885	0.875
superior vena	0.894	0.899	0.932	0.888	0.905	0.923	0.932

cava							
thyroid gland	0.832	0.886	0.908	0.866	0.853	0.89	0.886
vertebrae S1	0.87	0.906	0.925	0.89	0.88	0.909	0.915

S4: Extended Comparison of CT-FM against other approaches on the TotalSegmentatorV2 dataset

Collection ID	Number of Scans	Description
nlst	128037	The National Lung Screening Trial (NLST) dataset includes low-dose CT scans from a large, randomized trial evaluating lung cancer screening.
phantom_fda	3576	This collection contains CT scans of a Catphan phantom, used for quality control and standardization in imaging.
covid_19_ny_sbu	1753	The COVID-19 CT scan dataset from Stony Brook University, containing images of patients diagnosed with COVID-19.
ct_colonography	1711	This collection includes CT colonography scans, a minimally invasive method for colorectal cancer screening.
acrin_nsclc_fdg_pet	1283	The ACRIN NSCLC FDG-PET dataset contains both CT and PET scans of patients with non-small cell lung cancer from a clinical trial.
lidc_idri	974	The Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC) and Image Database Resource Initiative (IDRI) dataset includes lung CT scans with annotations by multiple radiologists.
4d_lung	830	This collection includes 4D (time-resolved) CT scans of the lung, capturing respiratory

		motion.
tcga_kirc	812	The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) Kidney Renal Clear Cell Carcinoma (KIRC) dataset contains CT and other images of patients with renal cell carcinoma.
lung_pet_ct_dx	546	This collection contains PET/CT scans of patients with suspected or confirmed lung cancer.
hcc_tace_seg	477	This collection includes CT scans of liver tumors from patients undergoing Transarterial Chemoembolization (TACE), with segmentation masks.
nsclc_radiogenomics	427	This dataset combines CT imaging with genomic data from patients with non-small cell lung cancer.
nsclc_radiomics	421	This collection of CT scans is related to radiomics analysis of patients with non-small cell lung cancer.
tcga_blca	409	The TCGA Bladder Urothelial Carcinoma (BLCA) dataset contains CT and other images from patients with bladder cancer.
cptac_ucec	393	The Clinical Proteomic Tumor Analysis Consortium (CPTAC) Uterine Corpus Endometrial Carcinoma (UCEC) dataset combines imaging with proteomic data.

tcga_ov	384	The TCGA Ovarian Cancer (OV) dataset includes CT and other images from patients with ovarian cancer.
c4kc_kits	366	The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) "C4KC" Kits collection includes phantom and clinical images for quantitative imaging analysis.
cptac_ccrcc	333	The CPTAC Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma (CCRCC) dataset includes CT and other imaging data linked to proteomic profiles.
tcga_ucec	330	The TCGA Uterine Corpus Endometrial Carcinoma (UCEC) dataset includes imaging data linked to genomic and clinical data.
cptac_pda	305	The CPTAC Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma (PDA) dataset combines proteomic and imaging data for pancreatic cancer patients.
pediatric_ct_seg	296	This collection contains pediatric CT scans with segmentation masks for various anatomical structures.
tcga_lihc	284	The TCGA Liver Hepatocellular Carcinoma (LIHC) dataset includes imaging and associated genomic data for patients with liver cancer.
acrinflt_breast	279	The ACRIN [1]8F-FLT Breast dataset contains PET/CT scans of breast

		cancer patients with additional [18F]-FLT tracer.
anti_pd_1_lung	265	This dataset includes CT scans from lung cancer patients treated with anti-PD-1 immunotherapy.
cmb_crc	251	The Cancer Moonshot Biobank (CMB) Colorectal Cancer (CRC) dataset includes CT scans of colorectal cancer patients with associated clinical data.
tcga_stad	237	The TCGA Stomach Adenocarcinoma (STAD) dataset includes imaging data linked to genomic information for stomach cancer.
rider_lung_pet_ct	235	The Radiological Image Database for Research (RIDER) Lung PET/CT dataset contains a collection of PET and CT scans of patients with lung cancer.
qiba_ct_1c	211	This is the Quantitative Imaging Biomarkers Alliance (QIBA) CT phantom study, containing CT scans from a multisite study.
pancreatic_ct_cbct_seg	200	This collection includes CT and Cone Beam CT (CBCT) scans of the pancreas with segmentation masks for various structures.
tcga_luad	183	The TCGA Lung Adenocarcinoma (LUAD) dataset contains CT and other images linked to genomic data from

		patients with lung adenocarcinoma.
stageii_colorectal_ct	181	This collection includes CT scans of patients with stage II colorectal cancer.
midrc_ricord_1a	163	Part of the Medical Imaging Data Resource Center (MIDRC), this collection includes COVID-19 CT scans (Phase 1a) along with clinical annotations.
cptac_lsc	159	The CPTAC Lung Squamous Cell Carcinoma (LSCC) dataset includes CT imaging and proteomic data for lung squamous cell carcinoma patients.
tcga_lusc	133	The TCGA Lung Squamous Cell Carcinoma (LUSC) dataset includes CT and other images linked to genomic data for patients with lung squamous cell carcinoma.
cptac_luad	133	The CPTAC Lung Adenocarcinoma (LUAD) dataset combines imaging with proteomic data for lung adenocarcinoma patients.
cmb_mel	124	The Cancer Moonshot Biobank (CMB) Melanoma (MEL) dataset includes CT scans of melanoma patients.
midrc_ricord_1b	118	Part of the Medical Imaging Data Resource Center (MIDRC), this collection includes COVID-19 CT scans

		(Phase 1b) along with clinical annotations.
pelvic_reference_data	116	This collection provides reference CT scans of the pelvic region.
covid_19_ar	113	This collection contains COVID-19 CT scans with associated metadata from patients in Argentina.
qin_breast	110	The Quantitative Imaging Network (QIN) Breast dataset contains imaging data from patients with breast cancer.
cmb_lca	107	The Cancer Moonshot Biobank (CMB) Lung Cancer Adenocarcinoma (LCA) dataset contains CT scans from lung cancer patients.
tcga_esca	94	The TCGA Esophageal Carcinoma (ESCA) dataset includes CT imaging data linked to genomic data from patients with esophageal cancer.
nsclc_radiomics_genomics	88	This dataset combines radiomics features extracted from CT scans with genomic data in non-small cell lung cancer.
naf_prostate	74	The dataset contains prostate MRIs from patients in a national active surveillance study.
ctpred_sunitinib_pannet	73	The dataset contains CT scans of patients with pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors (pNET) treated with

		Sunitinib.
spie_aapm_lung_ct_challenge	70	This collection is a challenge dataset for lung CT image analysis, containing scans from a SPIE-AAPM challenge.
cptac_cm	63	The CPTAC Cutaneous Melanoma (CM) dataset includes imaging data linked to proteomic and genomic data from melanoma patients.
rider_lung_ct	63	The RIDER Lung CT dataset contains CT scans of lung cancer patients collected from the RIDER project.
cptac_sar	63	The CPTAC Sarcoma (SAR) dataset combines imaging data with proteomic profiles of patients with sarcoma.
lctsc	60	This collection contains a longitudinal CT dataset of lung cancer patients from the Lung Cancer Therapy Study Consortium (LCTSC).
ct_vs_pet_ventilation_imaging	59	This collection contains CT and PET scans for assessment of ventilation imaging.
lungct_diagnosis	52	This collection contains a variety of lung CT scans for the task of diagnosis classification.
soft_tissue_sarcoma	51	This collection consists of soft tissue sarcoma CT scans.
tcga_kirp	47	The TCGA Kidney Renal Papillary Cell Carcinoma (KIRP) dataset includes CT and other images for

		patients with kidney papillary cell carcinoma.
qin_lung_ct	39	The Quantitative Imaging Network (QIN) Lung CT dataset contains scans from a clinical research study on lung cancer.
tcga_coad	37	The TCGA Colon Adenocarcinoma (COAD) dataset includes CT and other images linked to genomic data for colon cancer patients.
tcga_kich	33	The TCGA Kidney Chromophobe (KICH) dataset contains CT and other images linked to genomic data for kidney chromophobe carcinoma patients.
dro_toolkit	32	This collection provides some data and tools for use with the Data Release Orchestrator (DRO).
nsclc_radiomics_interobs erver1	22	This is a small dataset used to study interobserver variability in radiomics feature extraction from lung cancer CT scans.
cmb_mml	21	The Cancer Moonshot Biobank (CMB) Multiple Myeloma (MML) dataset includes CT scans of multiple myeloma patients.
breast_diagnosis	18	This collection is made of a small breast CT dataset for use in diagnosis tasks.
lung_fused_ct_pathology	15	This dataset contains CT scans of lung nodules matched to

		histopathology data.
tcga_prad	13	The TCGA Prostate Adenocarcinoma (PRAD) dataset contains CT and other images linked to genomic data for prostate cancer patients.
cmb_pca	12	The Cancer Moonshot Biobank (CMB) Prostate Cancer (PCA) dataset includes CT scans of prostate cancer patients.
tcga_thca	11	The TCGA Thyroid Carcinoma (THCA) dataset includes CT and other images from patients with thyroid cancer.
cmb_gec	8	The Cancer Moonshot Biobank (CMB) Gastroesophageal Cancer (GEC) dataset includes CT scans of gastroesophageal cancer patients.
pseudo_phi_dicom_data	4	This collection contains pseudo-anonymized DICOM data for testing DICOM data handling.
tcga_read	3	The TCGA Rectum Adenocarcinoma (READ) dataset contains imaging and genomic data from patients with rectal cancer.
tcga_sarc	3	The TCGA Sarcoma (SARC) dataset includes CT and other images from patients with sarcoma.
lung_phantom	1	This collection contains CT scans of a lung phantom.

S5: IDC collections used with the number of scans sourced from them and a short description of the collection.